

Fibrocystic Disease of the Male Breast: A Case Report and Literature Review of the Rare Entity

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ABSTRACT The breast is a complex structure, with numerous structural and functional elements, each a potential source of aberration or pathology. Fibrocystic disease of the breast is a common occurrence in women, often representing physiological changes. However, the entity is much more infrequent in men, with only a few cases reported in the literature. When found in men, fibrocystic disease is usually associated with endocrine disturbance, genotype abnormalities or the use of specific offending drugs. Here we report the case of a middle-aged male patient with unilateral fibrocystic disease of the breast with no identifiable causative factor and review the available literature about the rare entity. Thus, one must keep an open mind while approaching any case, so that unusual occurrences are not blatantly missed.

KEYWORDS fibrocystic disease, male breast, breast disease, benign breast disease

Introduction

Fibrocystic change is a condition that affects up to 50% of women and clinically varies from asymptomatic to pain or discomfort in the affected breast. The condition usually requires no treatment, except in the case of large, symptomatic or suspicious cysts. The condition is hormonally linked, hence much more infrequent in the male population, and like disorders of the breast in males in general, is usually ignored. In males, fibrocystic change is usually manifested due to excess estrogen states or pathological change in pre-existing gynaecomastia. As lobule derivatives of the breast are sparse in males, the associated pathologies too are infrequent, and usually secondary consequences of an underlying causative factor like a genetic or endocrine abnormality.

Case report

A 55-year-old male patient from South India presented with complaints of swelling and pain in the right breast for the last

one month, which was insidious in onset and gradually progressive. There was no history of similar complaints in the past or in the contralateral breast and no history of discharge from the nipple. The patient did not give any history of trauma or fever. The patient was being managed for bipolar affective disorder for the last 10 years with the tricyclic antidepressant Prothiaden (25mg twice a day) and the benzodiazepine Clonazepam (0.5mg twice a day). He did not suffer from any other comorbidities. He was a social drinker and did not smoke. He was married with two children.

General physical examination was unremarkable, except for grade I clubbing in all digits. On local examination, slight fullness was noted in the upper inner quadrant of the right breast, and the nipple-areolar complex was normal. Palpation revealed a 2x2 cm solitary, spherical, soft-to-firm swelling in the right periareolar region at the 2 o'clock position. The swelling was not fixed to the chest wall, mildly tender and did not exhibit signs of inflammation. No regional lymphadenopathy was appreciated, and the contralateral breast was normal. Secondary sexual characters were well-defined, and of the male pattern. Examination of the genitalia was normal, and both testes symmetrical, well-developed and of normal volume. There were no stigmata of chronic liver disease or occult malignancy.

With a presumptive diagnosis of gynecomastia, a routine pre-operative evaluation was commenced. Routine investigations done were within normal limits. Hormonal studies done including testosterone, prolactin, estrogen, progesterone, follicular stimulating hormone (FSH), Luteinising hormone (LH),

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Gonadotrophin releasing hormone (GnRH) and sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) were all unremarkable. Mammography elucidated a BI-RADS 2 lesion, and FNAC of the lesion was done, which revealed the fibrocystic change.

The patient then underwent excision of the lesion under general anaesthesia, with circumareolar skin incision placed, from 2'o clock to 5'o clock position. The lesion was well-circumscribed and easily dissected from surrounding normal breast tissue. The post-operative period was uneventful. Histopathological examination of the excised lesion was reported as fibrocystic disease.

Discussion

Fibrocystic disease of the breast is a common condition in females, characterized by stromal fibrosis, ductal branching, intra-ductal epithelial proliferation and cyst formation [1]. This is a rare finding in males, and very few cases have been reported in the literature.

Estrogen excess relative to progesterone is considered the causative factor for fibrocystic change in females, as estrogen stimulates proliferation of connective tissue as well as epithelial tissue [1]. The pathophysiology in males is poorly understood and may represent hormonal changes, paraneoplastic syndrome [2], or more probably a morphological variation of gynaecomastia [3]. No identifiable cause was present in our patient. A literature review with appropriate keywords did not reveal any link between the medication taken by the patient and fibrocystic change. Usually, the hormonally-associated disease tends to be bilateral and diffuse, whereas idiopathic lesions are unilateral and discrete [4]. In our case, the lesion was unilateral, discrete and belongs to the idiopathic category.

Lesions of breast lobules including cysts, fibroadenoma and lobular neoplasia are rare in men. However, sporadic cases of such lesions have been reported, usually with associated underlying gynaecomastia [2,3,4,5,6,7,8]. Histologically, fibrocystic disease exhibits both progressive and regressive changes simultaneously. The former includes fibrosis, cyst formation and epithelial proliferation; and the latter is characterised by sclerosing adenosis, alveolar atrophy and calcification [1]. Cyst formation occurs due to obstruction of ducts by stromal fibrosis [1]. Cyst fluid demonstrates various colours from serous, to milky, to green-blue, depending on the stage of the disease and degradation of the cyst contents [1]. Clinically, patients usually present with pain or tenderness in the breast, developing over several months or years. Patients also often have associated menstrual disturbance. Occasionally, the presentation is due to nipple discharge [1].

Diagnosis is based on imaging and histology. Mammography reveals a dense pattern. Darker specks reflect epithelial-proliferative and nodular changes amid dense white background ("buckshot" breast). Additionally, microcalcifications may also be present. Ultrasound of the breast reveals echo-dense, inhomogeneous areas of nodular-fibrosis and anechoic masses which represent the cysts. [1]. Needle aspiration is indicated in cases of diagnostic uncertainty or to rule out malignancy. In women with asymptomatic disease, only follow-up is required. Studies have shown that vitamin (specifically vitamin E) and iodine supplementation are beneficial [9]. For discrete, large or suspicious lesions, excision is the treatment of choice.

Conclusion

The breast is a complex structure, consisting of musculocutaneous, fibrous, structural and parenchymal tissue, besides neu-

rovascular and other support elements. Any of these can potentially give rise to local growths - benign and malignant - in both men and women, and all possibilities should be considered in patients of both sexes before proceeding with a definitive management plan. Although rare, lobule-derived lesions of the breast occasionally occur in male patients, usually with underlying gynaecomastia or in the setting of hormonal disturbance. After exclusion of malignancy, treatment principles mirror those applied in female patients, with excision of symptomatic or cosmetically displeasing lesions.

Competing Interests

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References

1. Vorherr, H. (1986). Fibrocystic breast disease: Pathophysiology, pathomorphology, clinical picture, and management. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 154(1), 161-179. doi:10.1016/0002-9378(86)90421-7
2. Bigotti G, Kasznica J. Sclerosing adenosis in the breast of a man with pulmonary oat cell carcinoma: report of a case. *Hum Pathol* 1986;17:861-3.
3. Robertson, K. E., Kazmi, S. A., & Jordan, L. B. (2009). Female-type fibrocystic disease with papillary hyperplasia in a male breast. *Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 63(1), 88-89. doi:10.1136/jcp.2009.071043
4. Bannayan, G.A. & Hadju, S.I. (1972). Gynecomastia: clinicopathological study of 351 cases. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 57,431.
5. Adibelli ZH, Oztekin O, Gunhan-Bilgen I, Postaci H, Uslu A, Ilhan E. Imaging characteristics of male breast disease. *Breast J*. 2010;16(5):510-8. 20560973
6. Banik S, Hale R. Fibrocystic disease in the male breast. *Histopathology*. 1988;12(2):214-6. 3366438
7. McClure J, Banerjee SS, Sandilands DG. Female type cystic hyperplasia in a male breast. *Postgrad Med J*. 1985;61(715):441-3.4022882
8. Shin SJ, Rosen PP. Bilateral presentation of fibroadenoma with digital fibroma-like inclusions in the male breast. *Arch Pathol Lab Med*. 2007;131(7):1126-9. 17617003
9. Ghent WR, Eskin BA, Low DA, Hill LP (October 1993). "Iodine replacement in fibrocystic disease of the breast". *Canadian Journal of Surgery (Comparative study)*. 36 (5): 453-60.